

Role of 3D Printed Concrete as a Sustainable Structure and Construction

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Abstract

The construction industry is at a pivotal point in its transition toward sustainable practices, driven by the need to reduce carbon emissions, resource consumption, and construction waste. 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP), an emerging digital fabrication technology, offers innovative solutions by enabling automated, layer-by-layer construction without the need for traditional formwork. This paper explores the role of 3D printed concrete in promoting sustainability across structural and environmental dimensions. It highlights the key benefits of 3DCP, including reduced material usage, minimized labor requirements, lower construction costs, and decreased environmental impact. The study also examines the integration of eco-friendly materials such as recycled aggregates, fly ash, geopolymers, and industrial byproducts into printable concrete mixtures, enhancing both sustainability and mechanical performance. In addition, the paper discusses technical challenges such as printability, structural integrity, and standardization, while presenting real-world applications and future directions. The findings demonstrate that 3DCP not only addresses many limitations of conventional construction methods but also represents a promising pathway toward green, efficient, and resilient built environments.

Keywords: *3D Concrete Printing (3DCP), Sustainable Construction, Additive Manufacturing, Eco-Friendly Materials, Green Building, Geopolymer Concrete, Low-Carbon Construction; Construction Automation.*

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Introduction

The global construction sector is undergoing a transformative shift toward sustainable practices to combat climate change, resource depletion, and inefficiencies. Traditional methods are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and environmentally damaging contributing up to 39% of global carbon emissions. In response, technological advances like 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP) have emerged as innovative tools to support green construction objectives. By integrating digital fabrication techniques with advanced cementitious materials, 3DCP enables precise, waste-minimized, and energy-efficient construction. This paper investigates the role of 3D printed concrete in achieving sustainability across structural performance, environmental impact, and construction economics.

With the continuous rise in global population and rapid urbanization, the demand for sustainable, affordable, and faster construction solutions is more urgent than ever before. Traditional construction techniques, while widely used, often suffer from inefficiencies, excessive material waste, high labor intensity, and a considerable environmental footprint, making them less suitable for the needs of modern, resource-constrained societies (Maghrabie, et al., 2021). Furthermore, conventional construction lacks effective waste management strategies and environmental safeguards, which are essential for mitigating the adverse impacts of building activities on ecosystems and climate change (Nutakki, et al., 2023; Mushtaha, et al., 2022). These challenges are particularly pronounced in developing regions, where limited financial and technical resources make it difficult to deliver sustainable and low-cost housing (Mohan, et al., 2021).

3D Concrete Printing (3DCP), an emerging form of additive manufacturing, presents a transformative solution to these challenges by enabling automated, layer-by-layer fabrication of concrete structures. This technology minimizes the need for formwork, reduces construction time, and enhances design flexibility, while significantly cutting down on material waste and labor requirements (Mohammad, Masad, & Al-Ghamdi, 2020; De Schutter, et al., 2018).

Through digital precision and automation, 3DCP not only improves the efficiency of the construction process but also contributes to reducing the environmental impact traditionally associated with cement-based construction.

Current research in 3DCP focuses on the development and application of sustainable concrete mixes tailored to the printing process. These include ordinary Portland cement (OPC), recycled aggregates, and geopolymers derived from industrial waste materials (Jayathilakage, Rajeev, & Sanjayan, 2022; Li, Li, & Zou, 2023; Robayo-Salazar, et al., 2023). OPC remains widely used due to its reliable setting and mechanical properties, such as compressive strength, resistance to harsh environmental conditions, and adaptability in shaping and molding (Bhattacharjee, et al., 2021). Aggregates, which form the bulk of concrete, directly influence its mechanical performance and are increasingly being replaced with recycled or industrial by-products to promote circular economy practices and reduce overall costs (Rahul, & Santhanam, 2020).

Additionally, geopolymers are gaining traction as eco-friendly alternatives to traditional binders. Formulated from fly ash, silica fume, slag, and other industrial by-products activated with alkaline solutions, geopolymer concrete exhibits competitive strength, durability, and significantly reduced carbon emissions compared to OPC-based systems (Marczyk, et al., 2021). The synergy between sustainable materials and digital fabrication using 3DCP offers immense potential for creating environmentally responsible, structurally efficient, and economically viable construction systems. By harnessing automated printing with sustainable mix designs, the construction industry can take a major step toward achieving low-carbon, resource-efficient, and resilient built environments.

Moreover, 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP) plays a pivotal role in advancing several of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, n.d.). These 17 globally adopted objectives aim to address critical issues such as poverty eradication, environmental preservation, and social equity by 2030 (Olabi, et

al., 2023). As an innovative construction technology, 3DCP contributes significantly to a number of these goals. For instance, its ability to deliver cost-effective, rapidly deployable, and resource-efficient housing solutions directly supports SDG 1 (No Poverty) by addressing the global housing deficit. Similarly, 3DCP can enhance SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being) by reducing occupational hazards on construction sites through automation and minimizing labor-intensive tasks.

A functional 3DCP system includes more than just printing materials. A 3DCP configuration includes a concrete mixer, The 3D printing process involves connecting pipes to a pump that provides material to a nozzle. The nozzle then prints the structure until it reaches its final shape. In addition to being environmentally friendly, 3D printing reduces waste. As shown in Figure 1, the suggested 3D printing holds the potential to reduce construction waste by 30–60%, labor expenses by 50–80%, and construction time by 50–70%.

Figure 1. A Comparison between the Construction Processes of 3D Printing and Conventional Construction

Source: Mohamed, & Mohamed (2025)

Materials and Methods

This study investigates the role of 3D printed concrete as a sustainable structural solution by analyzing existing materials used in 3D concrete printing (3DCP) and evaluating their environmental, mechanical, and economic performance. The methodology is structured around a comprehensive review of peer-reviewed literature, technical reports, and experimental case studies related to 3DCP material compositions and production techniques.

Materials

The selection and characterization of materials are critical in defining the mechanical, physical, and rheological properties of 3D printable

concrete. Evaluations include particle size distribution, density, morphology, and chemical composition analyzed using X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

Cement Replacements

OPC and PPC are the most commonly used binders in 3DCP. However, to align with sustainable practices, industrial by-products like GGBS, Fly Ash, and Silica Fume are increasingly used to partially replace cement, without compromising the mechanical integrity of the mix. The chemical composition of cementitious materials from different sources is presented in Table 1 of the source paper.

Table 1. Chemical Composition of Cement (OPC 53)

Composition	Hou, et al. (2021) (%)	Zhang, et al. (2018) (%)	Yu, et al. (2021) (%)	Zhu, et al. (2021) (%)
CaO	58.02	64.85	64.2	64.7
SiO ₂	23.148	21.65	20.4	20.4
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.56	4.32	3.2	3.38
Al ₂ O ₃	9.31	5.56	4.9	4.7
MgO	1.36	0.84	1.82	0.87
SO ₃	2.62	2.58	2.58	1.89
K ₂ O	1.02	0.76	0.38	0.49
Na ₂ O	0.411	0.24	0.24	0.33

Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS)

GGBS is a pozzolanic material obtained as a by-product from pig iron production, as shown in Figure 2. Approximately 300 kg of slag is generated per ton of pig iron (Panda, & Tan, 2018). It can replace 35–50% of OPC, offering enhanced early-age strength, chloride resistance, and crack resistance (Shen, et al., 2019; 2020; Mehta, et al., 2020). Its high content of CaO and SiO₂ (Table 2 - Appendix) ensures excellent reactivity, improving long-term durability and strength. GGBS also enhances resistance to alkali-silica reactions and sulphate attack, making it a valuable supplementary cementitious material (SCM).

Figure 2. Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS)

Fly Ash

Fly ash is widely used as a partial cement replacement, capable of replacing up to 40% of OPC (Nath, & Sarker, 2011; Kesharwani, et al.,

2017). However, higher contents increase setting time (Pati, Kale, & Suman, 2012). It enhances buildability and finish smoothness up to 35% usage (Melichar, et al., 2022), though it yields lower early-age strength than GGBS (Wang, Shi, & Wang, 2016). Fly ash contributes to durability due to lower calcium hydroxide formation and is also effective as a soil stabilizer in foundation applications (Sharma, & Sivapullaiah, 2016). As shown in Table 3 (Appendix) of the original document, its chemical composition further supports its role in enhancing the sustainability of concrete mixes (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Fly Ash

Silica Fume

Silica fume is another high-performance pozzolanic material that can replace OPC by 10–15% (Figure 4), improving yield stress and tensile bond strength (Sharma, 2018; Al-Eraky, et al., 2016; Shyam, Anwar, & Ahmad, 2017; Srinivas, et al., 2022). However, its lower bulk density and specific gravity make it less favorable

than GGBS and fly ash in large-volume printing applications (Table 4 - Appendix). All three materials conform to Indian Standards and have demonstrated success as SCMs in 3DCP (Nodehi, Ozbakkaloglu, & Gholampour, 2022; Bellum, et al., 2019; Anisur Rahman, 2017).

Figure 4. Silica Fume

Fine Aggregates

3DCP excludes coarse aggregates due to extrusion limitations. As a result, fine aggregates are used extensively, influencing the mixture's mechanical behavior. Coarse aggregates typically contribute up to 34% of conventional concrete strength (Prajapati, & Karanjit, 2019), so increasing cement and optimizing sand-to-

binder (s/b) ratios typically between 1.1 and 1.7 becomes essential (Rehman, & Kim, 2021).

Methodology

A standardized mix design approach was followed, considering three primary ratios: water-to-binder (w/b), sand-to-binder (s/b), and additive-to-binder (Christen, et al., 2022). The compressive strength and finish are heavily influenced by these proportions. Lower s/b ratios lead to higher strength, while optimal w/b ratios enhance workability (Khan, et al., 2018). The recommended s/b ratio range for 3DCP lies between 1.1 and 1.6.

Superplasticizers are added to reduce water demand, improving both strength and rheology. Slump flow tests are performed to assess workability (Malaeb, et al., 2015), and Viscosity Modifying Agents (VMAs) are added to further improve buildability.

Mixing Procedure

Materials are first dry-mixed, followed by the addition of water and superplasticizer. If VMAs are used in gel form, they are added with water; in dry form, they are sprinkled over the mix (Rahul, et al., 2019). Flowability is assessed using the flow table test (Gupthan, et al., 2022). If the mix appears dry, water is adjusted accordingly. Several trial mixes are conducted to determine the optimal formulation.

Figure 5. Rheological Properties Testing

Source: Samudrala, et al. (2023)

The finalized mix is tested for rheological properties, including extrudability, buildability, and open time, by printing slabs of 350 × 350 ×

120 mm and evaluating compressive and flexural strength (Lediga, & Kruger, 2017). The mix must meet target strength and setting time

requirements, while maximizing print quality and structural stability.

Acceptable printable regions are defined by evaluating the w/b and s/b ratios through experimental trials (Tay, Qian, & Tan, 2019). A typical sequence of rheological testing is outlined in Figure 5 of the source, and representative mix proportions with varying replacement levels are detailed in Table 5 (Appendix).

Additive Manufacturing and 3D Printing Technology

3D printing, also known as additive manufacturing (AM), is a transformative process that constructs three-dimensional objects by layering materials based on digital models (Pulse, (2013). In construction, this technology is still evolving but is rapidly becoming an integral part of modern design and fabrication workflows. Its potential to significantly improve construction speed, reduce costs, enhance safety, and minimize material waste positions it as a game-changer for the industry (Daminabo, et al., 2020). Historically, construction practices

underwent a major shift post-Industrial Revolution from slow, handcrafted buildings to mass-produced, standardized designs (Bhushan, & Caspers, 2017; Praveena, et al., 2022). While this transition improved efficiency, it often compromised uniqueness and customization. 3D printing, by contrast, merges mass production with custom design capabilities, enabling efficient, automated fabrication without sacrificing architectural individuality.

Unlike conventional subtractive methods that remove material to shape objects, 3D printing is inherently additive, building structures layer by layer. Different techniques are employed based on the material used extrusion and powder-based processes being the most prominent in construction applications. As shown in Figure 6 of the source, each AM method is categorized based on the materials involved and the deposition technique used (Bhushan, & Caspers, 2017; Jiménez, et al., 2019; Vora, & Sanyal, 2020; Espera, et al., 2019; Le-Bail, Maniglia, & Le-Bail, 2020).

Figure 6. Additive Manufacturing Classification

Source: Tabassum, & Mir, (2023)

A key focus of recent research is the sustainability potential of 3DCP. Environmentally friendly materials such as high-volume fly ash, geopolymers, and recycled glass

aggregates are being explored for their compatibility with 3D printing. These materials not only reduce carbon emissions but also enhance the mechanical and thermal

performance of printed structures. Furthermore, comparative studies of extrusion-based versus powder-based methods have revealed valuable insights into their respective strengths, limitations, and ideal applications in the construction domain. While extrusion is well-suited for large-scale structural components, powder-based techniques are more precise but currently less common in concrete applications. This comprehensive examination of 3D printing techniques within a sustainability framework has also identified critical research gaps, such as the need for standardization, structural validation, and long-term performance assessments. Addressing these gaps is essential for wider adoption and technological advancement. By integrating practical recommendations and focusing on sustainability, this review aims to serve as a reference point for researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers, encouraging further innovation in the field of 3D printed sustainable construction.

Costing of 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP)

Cost is a crucial consideration in evaluating the feasibility of any construction technique, and this holds true for 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP). The cost analysis of 3DCP structures involves multiple components, including material costs, printing, assembly, software, and labor, all of which vary across regions and project scales (Tabassum, & Mir, 2023).

Although the initial setup cost for 3DCP is generally higher than that of traditional methods, long-term savings may emerge from reduced manpower requirements and construction time. For example, studies have reported that prefabricated 3DCP houses in Japan cost approximately 8% more than conventional ones (Noguchi, 2003), while in Shanghai, a 3D printed building was constructed at a lower cost compared to its traditionally built counterpart (Wu, Wang, & Wang, 2016). These findings indicate that cost-effectiveness of 3DCP can be location- and context-dependent.

In India, the construction of an 1100 sq. ft. house using 3DCP cost around INR 23 lakhs, with an average material cost ranging between

INR 5000–7000 per m³ of concrete. While printing materials and equipment contribute to higher upfront costs (Buswell, et al., 2018), the automation of the construction process significantly reduces labor expenses. However, the reliance on specialized software and digital technologies introduces additional cost layers that must also be accounted for (Pearce, et al., 2010). Overall, despite some promising cost advantages in certain cases, a standardized cost assessment model or empirical formula is still lacking. Establishing such a framework is essential for determining the economic viability of 3DCP compared to conventional construction methods.

Case Studies: Global Applications of 3D Concrete Printing for Sustainable Construction

The implementation of 3D printed concrete (3DPC) in the construction of footbridges represents a cutting edge advancement in sustainable and automated construction. Currently, two main techniques have been employed in this domain: Contour Crafting Concrete Printing (CP) and D-Shape Printing. These methods enable precise fabrication of complex geometries with reduced material waste and labor. Noteworthy completed 3DPC footbridges include: Arch Footbridges: Alcobendas Spain, Shanghai China, Tianjin China, Venice Italy. Beam Footbridges: Gemert Netherlands, Nijmegen Netherlands, N243 Route Netherlands. Table 6 (Appendix): Provides technical specifications such as length, printing method, materials used, and construction duration (Asensio, et al., 2023).

These footbridges serve as landmark demonstrations of 3DCP's ability to achieve structural efficiency, design freedom, and sustainability through reduced CO₂ emissions and material usage. Additionally, several of these structures utilized topology optimization and recycled materials, aligning with the global sustainable development goals (SDGs). Figure 7: Illustrates the visual layout and design form of each 3D printed footbridge. These projects reflect the real-world scalability of 3DCP in civil infrastructure and underscore its potential in

bridging the gap between digital design and sustainable construction.

Figure 7. 3DPC footbridge projects: (a) Parque de Castilla (credit: Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia, IAAC); (b) Gemert (credit: Marc Zoutendijk); (c) Wisdom Bay Park (credit: Tsinghua University); (d) Zhaozhou (credit: Xinhua); (e) Striatus (credit: naaro); (f) The Bridge Project (credit: Municipality of Nijmegen); and (g) N243 route (credit: Witteveen+Bos)

Challenges in 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP)

Despite its promising potential, 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP) faces several technical and practical challenges that hinder its widespread adoption. One of the primary obstacles is the complexity of accurate cost estimation, which makes it difficult to evaluate the economic feasibility of 3DCP compared to traditional methods (De Schutter, et al., 2018). Material-related issues, such as shrinkage and cracking, are more prevalent in 3DCP, affecting both durability and structural performance.

Additionally, the rheological behavior of fresh concrete specifically, its pumpability, extrudability, and buildability requires careful control and is often difficult to maintain consistently. The anisotropy (direction-dependent properties) of printed elements also poses concerns for long-term strength and durability (Panda, Paul, & Tan, 2017).

Another significant challenge lies in the lack of standardized testing protocols and codal guidelines for 3DCP. This results in higher testing costs and difficulties in validating performance under real-world conditions. The use of specialized thermal insulation materials like polyurethane further complicates material procurement, potentially delaying construction timelines.

Environmental concerns have also emerged. Although 3DCP reduces labor and material waste, the energy consumption and embodied carbon footprint associated with certain materials and processes can be higher than those in conventional construction methods (Han, et al., 2021). Furthermore, inconsistencies between laboratory-scale performance and site-scale implementation especially in terms of open time and printability pose additional limitations (Xiao, et al., 2021). Lastly, high ambient temperatures during printing can lead to rapid water evaporation, resulting in cracks and a decrease in concrete strength (Xiao, et al., 2022). While 3DCP holds significant promise for sustainable construction, addressing these technical, environmental, and regulatory challenges is essential for advancing its commercial and structural viability.

While 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP) offers notable cost savings during the construction phase, one of the major barriers to its widespread adoption is the high initial investment required for advanced printing equipment. The precision, scale, and complexity of 3DCP systems demand extensive research and development, which can significantly increase upfront costs. Moreover, on-site (in situ) printing introduces additional constraints. Environmental factors such as weather conditions, site accessibility, and terrain stability can affect the reliability and consistency of the

printing process. Any mechanical failure or damage to the printer can result in costly maintenance and extended downtime, disrupting project timelines and adding to operational expenses. Thus, while 3DCP has demonstrated strong potential for sustainable construction, the technological and logistical limitations of the printing equipment remain a significant challenge requiring ongoing innovation and investment (Nawaz, et al., 2024).

Conclusion

The evolution of 3D Concrete Printing (3DCP) marks a transformative shift in the construction industry, offering a sustainable and efficient alternative to conventional building methods. This research has demonstrated that 3DCP significantly contributes to environmental sustainability by reducing material waste, minimizing labor dependency, and enabling the incorporation of eco-friendly and industrial byproduct-based materials such as GGBS, fly ash, and geopolymers. These innovations not only lower the environmental footprint of concrete production but also enhance the mechanical and thermal performance of printed structures.

Through the examination of material selection, mix design methodologies, and additive manufacturing techniques, it is evident that 3DCP supports the realization of complex, cost-effective, and resilient architectural forms. Despite the initial high setup costs and technological barriers, including issues of printability, anisotropy, cracking, and lack of codified standards, the long-term economic and ecological advantages make 3DCP a compelling solution for future construction practices.

Moreover, the technology aligns well with several UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), addressing concerns related to affordable housing, climate action, and responsible consumption. However, for 3DCP to be widely adopted, further advancements in equipment affordability, standardization, and large-scale implementation strategies are required. In conclusion, 3D Concrete Printing holds immense potential in reshaping the built environment by bridging the gap between digital innovation and sustainable development. With

continued research, policy support, and technological refinement, 3DCP can pave the way toward greener, smarter, and more inclusive construction paradigms globally.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest

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Appendix

Table 2. Chemical Composition of GGBS (%)

CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	SO ₃	TiO ₂	K ₂ O	Carbon	Ref
39.37	29.65	15.56	0.35	7.54	0–1.04	4.32	0–1.04	0–1.04	0	Mehta, et al. (2020)
34.8	37.5	6.4	0.51	8.6	0.38	0	0	0.9	0	Ramezaniapour, et al. (2016)
37.73	34.62	11.82	2.73	9.43	0.35	1.42	0	0.5	0	Shen,et al. (2020)

Table 3. Chemical Composition of Fly Ash (%)

CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	SO ₃	TiO ₂	K ₂ O	Carbon	Ref
3.10	36.10	25.03	8.66	1.24	0	0.59	0.91	1.08	23.29	Tudjono, Purwanto, & Apsari, (2014)
2.61	52.11	23.59	7.39	0.78	0–1.2	0	0	0–1.2	0	Nizar, et al. (2014)
0.6–9	50.2–59.7	14–32.4	2.7–16.6	0.1–2.3	0.2–1.2	0	0.3–2.7	0.2–4.7	0	Bhatt, A., et al. (2019)

Table 4. Chemical Composition of Silica Fume (%)

CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	SO ₃	TiO ₂	K ₂ O	Carbon	Ref
0.1–0.5	86–96	0.4–1	0.1–1.5	0.3–2	0.4–0.5	0.1–0.4	0	0.3–3	0.5–2.5	Anisur Rahman, (2017)
0.69	93.35	0.92	0.71	0.72	0.33	0.13	0	0.86	0	Nagrokiene, et al. (2019)
0.94	92.6	0.89	1.97	0.96	0	0.33	0.25	1.31	0.07	Wan Husin, Johari, & Ibrahim, (2016)

Table 5. Quantity of Materials per m³

Cement (kg)	GGBS (kg)	Silica Fume (kg)	Limestone Sand (kg)	Aggregate (kg)	Water (kg)	Superplasticizer (kg)	VMA (kg)	Recycled Sand (kg)	Fibres (kg)	Ref
483	314	70	447	284	347	3.47	5.2	-	-	Van Overmeir, et al. (2022)
458	377	51	195	549	355	2.66	2.66	-	-	Van Overmeir, et al. (2022)
1000	0	0	0	1000	350	1.12	1.28	-	20	Ding, et al. (2021)
1000	0	0	0	1000	420	0.86	1.28	500	5	Ding, et al. (2021)

1000	0	0	0	1000	420	1	1.28	500	10	Ding, et al. (2021)
1000	0	0	0	1000	420	1.24	1.28	500	20	Ding, et al. (2021)
1000	0	0	0	1000	420	2.18	1.28	500	28	Ding, et al. (2021)
815	0	0	0	1222	285	4.24	0.81	-	-	Mohan, et al. (2021)
815	0	0	0	1222	285	2.85	0.81	-	-	Mohan, et al. (2021)

Table 6. Completed 3DPC Footbridge Constructions

Project	Location	Opening year	Span (m)	Designer	Construction company	Typology	Ref.
Footbridge “Parque de Castilla”	Alcobendas (Spain)	2016	12.0	ACCIONA (ES). IAAC (ES). UPC (ES)	Acciona (ES). D-Shape (IT)	Arch	De la Fuente, et al. (2022)
Footbridge Gemert	Gemert (Holland)	2017	8.0	Witteveen+Bos (NL). TU/e (NL)	BAM Infra (NL). Weber Beamix (NL)	Beam	Bos, et al. (2017); Salet, et al. (2018)
Footbridge “Wisdom Bay Park”	Shanghai (China)	2019	14.4	Tsinghua University (CN)	N/A	Arch	Tsinghua University, School of Architecture (2019)
Footbridge Zhaozhou	Tianjin (China)	2019	17.9	Hebei University of Technology (CN)	Hebei University of Technology (CN)	Arch	Tsinghua University, School of Architecture (2019)
Striatus	Venice (Italy)	2021	15.1	BRG (CH). ZHACODE (UK)	Incremental3D (AT). Holcim	Arch	Hager, Golonka, & Putanowicz, (2016)
The Bridge Project	Nijmegen (Holland)	2021	5.7	Michiel van der Kley (NL). Witteveen+Bos (NL). TU/e (NL)	BAM Infra (NL). Weber Beamix (NL)	Beam	Hager, Golonka, & Putanowicz, (2016)
Footbridges of N243 route	N243 (Holland)	N/A	11.0	Witteveen+Bos (NL). TU/e (NL)	BAM Infra (NL). Weber Beamix (NL)	Beam	Hager, Golonka, & Putanowicz, (2016)

